

PACKET LOSS RESILIENT H.263+ COMPLIANT VIDEO CODING

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ABSTRACT

This paper considers the problem of real-time point to point video transmission over the public Internet. A set of techniques in the direction of packet loss resilience of video compressed streams is presented. Aiming at a best trade-off between compression efficiency and packet loss resilience, a procedure for adapting the video coding modes and quantizer parameters to varying network characteristics is introduced. The network adaptive coding modes and quantizers selection is based on a rate-distortion procedure with global distortion metrics incorporating channel characteristics under the form of a packet loss model. The method has been implemented in a H.263+ software video encoder. As a second step, the coding mode selection strategy is refined by exploiting feedback information which consists in indicating lost video packets. We show that exploiting this knowledge of the channel state allows to significantly improve the robustness of H.263+ video streams in a packet loss prone environment.

1 INTRODUCTION

Various approaches have emerged recently in order to improve the quality of video transmission over erasure channels such as packet switched networks, characterized by packet losses or erasures (e.g. the single class best effort service provided by today's Internet). The main underlying concept is the adaptation of the video applications to the service provided by the network. A first approach consists in adapting the rate of the video source to the available network capacity, taking often into account considerations of fair share of the bandwidth with competing TCP-based traffic. This property is known under the name of TCP-friendliness.

Rate adaptation leads to reduced loss rates, however do not avoid losses. It is therefore necessary to develop in addition robust video coding schemes, in order to minimize the impact of the losses on the reconstructed signals. As an example, in order to avoid temporal loss propagation, video-conferencing tools, currently used on the Mbone, do not support temporal prediction but rely instead on simple Conditional Replenishment[4]. This

method obviously improves the robustness of the compressed streams to losses, but at the price of a significant penalty in terms of compression efficiency. Similarly, a coding option of the H.263 version 2 encoder, consists in intra refreshing a random set of macro-blocks, while all macro-blocks have to be intra updated within a fixed number of frames [2]. The use of this option is improved in [7], where the random Intra update rate is optimized, taking into account the networks characteristics.

However, this coding option, on the best-effort Internet, may turn out to be not sufficient, because of the random choice of the macro-blocks to be updated, which doesn't reflect the scene activity. On the other hand, other mode selection schemes, based on the use of a packet loss model, have been presented in the literature [1, 3]. They both intend to achieve a better trade-off between robustness and compression. Our first attempt for maintaining temporal prediction in a loss-prone environment, which consists in a coding mode selection algorithm, adaptive to time-varying network characteristics, has been developed in [3]. A TCP-friendly congestion control mechanism provides the time-varying network bandwidth constraint. The network loss characteristics are captured on a sliding temporal window and modeled with a two-state Markov model, known under the name of Elliott-Gilbert. The model is introduced in a metric reflecting both the coding distortion and the channel-induced distortion. The best mode (INTRA or INTER) is then selected in order to minimize the overall distortion under the bandwidth constraint set by the congestion control mechanism. The algorithm, incorporated in an MPEG-4 encoder, has provided significant improvements both in terms of SNR and visual quality, in presence of losses.

In this paper, the above adaptive coding mode selection algorithm is first extended to a network adaptive joint mode and quantization parameter optimization. This extension, allowing a fine tuning of the bit rate, significantly improves the performances of the algorithm on a finite state erasure channel. As a second step, the incorporation of a feedback message in the RTCP receiver report packets is considered, in order to increase

the reliability of the joint mode and quantization parameters adaptation. It is proposed here to extend the syntax and semantic of the RTCP receiver report packet, by incorporating a simple backward message that would consist in the sequence number of the first packet lost in a given temporal window. The feedback information can then be exploited in the encoder, by estimating the impact of the loss propagation on the following frames.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 investigates the joint coding mode and quantization parameters selection scheme that we have designed. Section 3 introduces the RTCP's syntax extension we propose, and the strategy adopted to incorporate the feedback information into the mode selection process. Section 4 presents some experimental results. Future work indications and concluding remarks are given in section 5.

2 NETWORK ADAPTIVE JOINT CODING MODE AND QUANTIZER SELECTION

A coding mode selection algorithm has been introduced in [3], in order to optimize the trade-off between packet loss resilience and compression efficiency. It consists in combining CR with an intra/inter-coding mode decision mechanism based on a rate-distortion optimization procedure that takes into account the varying channel loss characteristics, captured on a sliding temporal window. The rate-distortion optimization is performed under varying channel bandwidth constraints given by a TCP-friendly congestion control mechanism. In order to reduce the encoder complexity, the coding mode decision is preceded by a motion detection process which pre-selects a subset of macro-blocks to be encoded. However, one difficulty in this approach resides in the choice of the thresholds used in the motion detection, for different varying loss conditions.

In order to overcome this difficulty, the motion detection process has been removed, and the optimization process is reformulated in a more general way, as follows.

Let $\mathcal{I} = \{INTRA, INTER, UNCODED\}$, be the set of possible coding modes for each macro-block (MB) of a group of MBs $\mathcal{X} = (X_1, \dots, X_N)$. A combination of coding modes for the GOB $\mathcal{X}$ is an element $\mathcal{M} = (M_1, \dots, M_N) \in \mathcal{I}^N$. Similarly, a set of quantization parameters for the GOB $\mathcal{X}$ is an element $\mathcal{Q} = (Q_1, \dots, Q_N) \in [1..31]^N$.

The selection process is extended towards a joint optimization of both the coding modes and the quantization parameters Q_i , in the rate-distortion sense. The distortion measure used here reflects both the quantization distortion and the channel-induced distortion, for the varying loss characteristics measured on the sliding temporal window. Adopting a Bernoulli process to model the channel loss characteristics, let P_e be the average packet loss probability on a given temporal window. Let X_i^t be the original macro-block at spatial location i and frame number. We call $\hat{X}_i^t$ the result of inverse

quantization of X_i^t and $\hat{\tilde{X}}_i^t$ the concealed version of $\hat{X}_i^t$ at the decoder side, when a packet loss occurs. The concealment method used here consists in treating erroneous macro-blocks as uncoded. The distortion for an intra-coded macro-block can be expressed as

$$D(X_i^t, INTRA, Q_i^t) = (1 - P_e) \left| X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^t \right| + P_e \left| X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^{t-1} \right|, \quad (1)$$

where $|\cdot|$ denotes the mean square error of an MB, and Q_i^t is the quantization parameter associated to the MB X_i^t . For an inter-coded MB, it has been shown in [3] that the distortion value is upper bounded as

$$D(X_i^t, INTER, Q_i^t) \leq (1 - P_e)^k \left| X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^t \right| + (1 - (1 - P_e)^k) \left| X_i^t - \hat{X}_i^{t-k} \right|, \quad (2)$$

where k is the number packets sent on the network and containing at least one MB at spatial location i , and where $\hat{X}_i^{t-k}$ is the inverse quantized version of last intra-MB at location i . Given the above distortion measures, the problem is then of finding the best combination of coding modes and quantization parameters, for the subset of MBs $\mathcal{X}$, and can be formulated as the minimization

$$\min_{\mathcal{M}, \mathcal{Q}} D(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{M}, \mathcal{Q}) \quad \text{subject to} \quad R(\mathcal{X}, \mathcal{M}) \leq R_c$$

where D and R represent respectively the distortion and rate measures, and where R_c represents the bit budget allocated to the GOB and provided by the TCP-friendly congestion control mechanism. The above rate constrained optimization problem is rewritten as an unconstrained Lagrangian formulation, and solved as a usual rate allocation problem. Note that, in order to meet real-time encoding constraints, rate-distortion models of the quantizer performances, inspired from [6], are used in the rate-distortion framework, without any significant loss of performances.

3 FEEDBACK-BASED PACKET LOSS RECOVERY

3.1 Extension of the RTCP Receiver Report

A possible extension of the RTCP receiver report packet, by incorporating a simple backward message is considered in order to improve the reliability of the above network adaptive joint mode and quantization parameter selection algorithm. This extension consists in incorporating in the Receiver Report an additional field that contains the sequence number of the first packet lost in a given temporal window. The temporal window considered is the time interval on which the network statistic information, provided in the standardized RTCP Receiver Reports, is normally computed, and is in line with RTCP bandwidth scalability considerations. Note that

here, unlike the NEWPRED approach described in [8], the backward message channel would be non specific to a given type of streams (e.g. video) but could be exploited for any type of multimedia streams (e.g. audio, speech).

3.2 Feedback-based mode selection

Two approaches are proposed in [8] to exploit feedback information in order to limit temporal propagation of transmission errors. The NEWPRED method [8] consists in indicating a frame that has not been correctly decoded. A reference picture is then selected by the encoder, in order to suppress temporal error propagation due to inter-frame coding. This assumes that several reconstructed frames are stored both by the encoder and the decoder, and the choice of the reference frame for prediction is signaled via the H.263+ syntax. However, not only this method could not be easily extended to a multi-cast transmission scenario, but also it implies the use of the feedback messages specifically designed for video streams. Secondly, an error tracking technique, described in [8], intends to determine the damaged areas in the last coded frame when lost macro-blocks are reported. The reconstruction error of macro-blocks of the last coded frame is then estimated, and is considered in the mode decision of the following frame. This error estimation takes into account the dependencies between macro-blocks of successive frames, but remains approximative.

The strategy proposed here, in order to exploit the feedback information, relies on the idea that when a packet loss is reported to the video source, it refers to some video data that has formerly been encoded and transmitted. More precisely, the loss temporal propagation window depends on the encoding, transmission, decoding and re-transmission delays. Hence, we decide to trace the dependencies between successive frames, due to predictive coding, in order to estimate the visual impact of a given loss on the current frame. The frame number and the address of macro-blocks contained in each RTP packet are stored by the encoder. The dependencies between macro-blocks of successive frames are also continuously recorded in the following way. The block-matching process provides, for each macro-block X , a reference macro-block $\hat{X}_{ref}$, in the previously reconstructed frame. If $\hat{X}_{ref}$ is not aligned on the 16×16 pixels grid, then we determine the four macro-blocks of the grid which are overlapped by $\hat{X}_{ref}$. This is illustrated in Fig.1, where macro-block 1 of frame $t - 1$ depends on macro-blocks 1, 2, 3 and 4 in frame $t - 2$. As a consequence, if any of these four macro-blocks is lost, then the macro-block 1 in frame $t - 1$ cannot be reconstructed by the decoder and an error concealment has to be applied. Given these dependencies extracted by motion estimation, an oriented graph is constructed, where the nodes represent macro-blocks positions. The graph's edges represent temporal prediction dependen-

Figure 1: Dependencies among macro-blocks of successive frames.

cies between macro-blocks. For instance, Fig.2 depicts the graph structure derived from Fig.1. Hence, when a

Figure 2: Graph structure derived from dependencies of Fig.1. Each node corresponds to a spatial and temporal macro-block position.

feedback message is received, the damaged MBs in the last coded frame are captured by a recursive search algorithm. The set of corrupted macro-blocks found in the last coded frame is then intra refreshed in the current frame. The remaining macro-blocks of the current frame are coded via the mode and quantizer selection algorithm defined in section 2. Note that, unlike the NEWPRED approach, our strategy can more easily be extended to a multi-cast scenario. Moreover, this intra refreshment algorithm is better adapted to real-time requirements than classical Automatic Repeat Request (ARQ) schemes.

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The H.263+ Test Model version 3.2.0, the CR, the network adaptive mode and quantization parameters selection algorithm described in section 2, and the feedback-based extension described in section 3 have been used for encoding the QCIF Coastguard and News sequences at a constant bit-rate of 100Kbits/s. The frame rate of all sources is 10 frames/s. The H.263+ encoder is used with the random INTRA update option described in section 1, and the TMN8 Rate Control algorithm [6]. The finite state erasure channel is simulated by an Elliott-Gilbert model with transition probabilities $p = 0.08$ and

Figure 3: Performances (PSNR) on Finite State Erasure Channels

$q = 0.60$. Fig. 3 respectively depicts the average PSNR values as a function of the loss rate obtained with all encoders, when encoding Coastguard and News sequences. In an error-free environment, the intra coding mode makes the CR be less efficient than the other coders. In presence of losses, the H.263+ performances fall below the others for both sequences. CR, which is naturally resilient to packet losses, keeps an average quality almost constant. In the case of the Coastguard sequence, the two encoders using the mode selection procedure give similar results to CR, because of the high motion in the scene, which brings about a large amount of intra coded MBs. Moreover, concerning the News sequence, the network adaptive mode and quantization parameters selection allows to improve the trade-off between compression efficiency and packet loss resilience, in comparison with the first three encoders. Finally, the introduction of feedback information in the selection leads to a even higher packet loss resilience. Visually, it allows to suppress persistent reconstruction errors that can happen with the mode selection process. Note that the algorithm can be easily adapted to other feedback messages, as proposed in [5]. This feedback message consists in a mask of 16 bits indicating lost and received packet on a given temporal window. As all packet losses are then re-

ported, this new type of Receiver Report would allow to improve again our feedback-based refreshment strategy.

5 CONCLUSION

This paper has presented a network adaptive joint coding mode and quantization parameters selection, in order to obtain a good trade-off between packet loss resilience and compression performances. The coding parameters selection is based on a rate-distortion optimization with a distortion metric that takes into account the channel state. This selection process is refined by a feedback-based mode selection mechanism, based on the receipt of feedback messages indicating lost video packets. Experimental results show that exploiting the knowledge of time-varying channel characteristics, under the form of a loss model, and also through the use of some feedback information, leads to an improved overall quality of service in a non-scalable video transmission scheme. Next step consists in adapting the feedback-based mode selection process to other types of Receiver Reports. Finally, current is dedicated to the extension of the developed techniques to enhancement layers of the scalable H.263+ encoder.

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